

Demonstration of Multi-Access 6G Networks with User Mobility Considerations

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Abstract— This paper demonstrates the development of a multi-technology radio access network (RAN) integrating 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies to support a diverse set of mobile UEs. UEs with various mobility patterns are attached to the network requesting the establishment of end-to-end (E2E) slices with the Data Network (DN). In case where UEs are attached to the 3GPP access network, the corresponding slices are established over paths formed by interconnecting the gNB, User Plane Function (UPF) and DN nodes. However, in case where UEs select a non-3GPP network, their connectivity with the DN is achieved through the Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF), that ensures secure communication and facilitates smooth integration with the overall network architecture. To solve the optimal network selection problem, a resource allocation policy is proposed that tries to jointly minimize the blocking and dropping rates for slow and fast, respectively, moving UEs. The overall process is theoretically evaluated using a two-dimensional Markov Chain (MC). Finally, a cloud-based 5G testbed has been used to validate the performance of the whole system providing insights into E2E performance and resource consumption.

Keywords— 5G, non-3GPP Access, N3IWF, 5G-RAN, 5G Core, Queuing Theory.

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

5G Networks are designed to operate in highly heterogeneous environments, supporting a wide array of services across different sectors and vertical industries, including enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC). To achieve these diverse service requirements, 5G incorporates a heterogeneous network (HetNet) architecture, which leverages various radio access technologies (RATs). These include traditional cellular technologies such as LTE and 5G New Radio (NR) as well as non-3GPP access technologies like Wi-Fi, satellite, and other wireless networks. Seamless interworking between 5G and other industry access technologies helps minimize operational costs, facilitating the widespread adoption of 5G Non-Public Networks (NPNs) in vertical domains that already employ non-3GPP access technologies, like WiFi. This integration allows end-devices that lack 5G capabilities, such as legacy and IoT devices, to access the 5G network and benefit from the above 5G scenarios.

A critical component in the 5G architecture that enables seamless integration of untrusted non-3GPP access technologies is the Non-3GPP Interworking Function

(N3IWF) [1]. The N3IWF plays a pivotal role in ensuring that devices can connect to the 5G Core (5GC) network via non-3GPP access networks. It acts as a bridge, providing secure and efficient interworking between non-3GPP access networks and the 5GC. The N3IWF supports key functionalities such as user authentication, data encryption, and secure tunneling, which are essential for maintaining the integrity and security of the network while facilitating seamless mobility and service continuity.

In addition to N3IWF, other elements within the 5GC network, such as the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) and the User Plane Function (UPF), also contribute to managing connectivity and mobility across different access technologies. AMF handles connection management and mobility procedures, while UPF manages the user plane traffic, ensuring efficient data routing and low-latency communication.

Integration of non-3GPP technologies with the 5G Core have been tackled recently by a number of researchers. Most of the reported work attempts to verify the feasibility of such deployments with various Access Network (AN) technologies. A relevant tutorial article focusing on the convergence of non-3GPP ANs with the 5GC is presented in [6]. The authors classify the types of non-3GPP access in three categories i.e. trusted, untrusted and wireline. They also discuss several aspects such as authentication and authorization procedures as well as PDU session establishment. Finally, they present an experimental environment that interconnects the 5GC with Wi-Fi along with a basic performance evaluation. A testbed that combines elements from different 5GC open-source projects and integrate these with non-3GPP access technologies such as Wi-Fi is presented in [7]. The authors use their testbed implementation to investigate various security aspects. Authors in [9] demonstrate an implementation that integrates LiFi and 5G which is suitable for Smart Factory scenarios. They also present a multistage demonstrator set-up in order to evaluate the protocol stack enhancements that are needed to support handover between LiFi and 5G. Finally, the authors in [10] propose the integration of a Very Short Aperture Link (VSAT) Satellite link with 5GC. They discuss various parameters that are needed to enable this integration such as the protocol stack and signaling procedures. Moreover, they present an implementation that interconnects the N3IWF with a satellite emulator.

Figure 1: 5G Network Topology

In mobile environments where users exhibit varying mobility patterns and service requirements, efficient network selection and handover management are crucial to minimizing service interruption and resource consumption. Factors influencing Radio Access Technology (RAT) selection include service requirements such as bandwidth and latency, real-time network conditions like signal strength and congestion levels, cost considerations, and the need for seamless mobility management between RATs.

One of the relevant challenges that need to be addressed involves managing handovers between cells. As users move through the network, frequent handovers can lead to interruptions and degraded service quality. This challenge is magnified when considering handovers between 3GPP and non-3GPP networks. Effective cell management strategies, such as dynamic handover algorithms and intelligent traffic steering, are essential to minimize these disruptions and maintain seamless connectivity.

Various works exist in the literature for addressing optimal multi-RAT selection in 5G/B5G systems. [11], focuses on the logical evolution of 5G networks. The authors propose a novel scheme that provides to the user the ability to select between various access technologies. Moreover, they discuss the integration of analytics as a means to enhance E2E performance. The authors in [12] discuss multi-connectivity features and propose a flexible architecture that offers connectivity through various technologies such as 5G, LTE and WiFi as a way to optimize throughput, mobility and resource management aspects. A solution that offers two connectivity paths, one through LiFi and one through standard 5G components is presented in [13], as well as a handover mechanism between licensed and unlicensed access technologies. The proposed solution is suitable for industrial and private applications. Finally, in [14] a model is proposed based on queuing network theory that aims at optimizing the design and planning of multiservice RANs with diverse network requirements in dense areas.

The present study investigates access network selection strategies aiming at reducing handover

interruptions by leveraging experimental data from an opensource 5G platform. Our results have been produced using real user mobility statistics as well as lab-based profiling measurements of a 5G infrastructure that supports non-3GPP access. By analyzing resource consumption for both non-3GPP and 5G networks and applying queuing theory, we can derive insights regarding end-to-end performance and optimize handover processes to ensure seamless user experiences.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: in *Section II* we describe the system architecture. *Section III* presents the analytical framework based on queuing theory for E2E performance analysis. *Section IV* discusses the implementation and evaluates the proposed model. Finally, *Section V* concludes the paper.

II. INTEGRATION OF 5G SYSTEMS AND NON-3GPP ACCESS NETWORKS: AN OVERVIEW

A. 5G Network Architecture

5G systems introduce several architectural advancements compared to previous generations (3G/4G), incorporating numerous new concepts and technologies to meet the extensive variety of applications they are designed to support. As illustrated in Figure 1, the overall 5G network architecture adopts microservices and Network Function (NF) decomposition, allowing flexible scaling and updates without disrupting existing services. This approach ensures adaptability and efficiency across the network.

The adopted 5G-RAN solution embraces functional splitting, with a "vertical split" for Control and User Plane Separation (CUPS) and a "horizontal split" allowing to divide the baseband function stack into a set of functions [2]. This facilitates the baseband function to be distributed across different elements, namely the Remote Unit (RU), the Distributed Unit (DU) and the Central Unit (CU) based on service requirements, enhancing resource and energy efficiency. The RU is responsible for the RF processing, while the DU handles lower layer-2 protocols and physical layer processing. The non-real-time upper layer processing and core network functions are managed by the CU. New logical interfaces, such as the fronthaul (O-FH) and F1 interfaces, support connectivity between the RUs and DUs and DUs and CUs respectively. This flexible architecture allows the 5G base station (gNB) to be deployed in two ways: either monolithically, where CU, DU, and RU are co-located, or disaggregated, where they are distributed across different locations. The latter allows a more flexible mapping of NFs to physical network entities, tailored to specific use cases and deployment constraints [3].

The 5GCN also adopts CUPS, leveraging virtualization and softwarization. This enables the 5GCN to be seen as a collection of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), capitalizing on the benefits of cloudified and cloud-native deployments. The Control Plane (CP) consists of VNFs that are responsible for decision-making and network management and adopts a Service-Based Architecture (SBA) [5]. This means that the VNFs

communicate in order to exchange services and information through a Service-Based Interface (SBI). Key VNFs in the CP include [4], [17],[18]:

- the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), which handles user registration, connection, and mobility management and handovers.
- the Session Management Function (SMF), which manages session establishment, modification, and release.
- the Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF), which plays critical roles in network slicing.
- the Policy Control Function (PCF), which performs policy enforcement, managing rules and policies.
- the Authentication Server Function (AUSF), which handles authentication processes.
- the Unified Data Management (UDM), which manages user data and authentication keys.
- the Network Exposure Function (NEF), that provides a standardized interface for external applications and services to interact with 5GCN.
- the Network Repository Function (NRF). It manages the registration and discovery of NFs within 5GCN.
- the Application Function (AF). The AF interacts with the 5G core to provide application-specific services.
- the N3IWF: The N3IWF allows user devices to connect to the 5G core network via non-3GPP access networks.

The User Plane (UP) of the 5GCN consists of the User Plane Function (UPF), that manages the data path between the User Equipment (UE) and the Data Network (DN), establishing and maintaining Packet Data Unit (PDU) sessions for user mobility. Controlled by the SMF via the Packet Forwarding Control Protocol (PFCP), the UPF handles traffic management policies and rules. It maps traffic to appropriate tunnels based on Quality of Service (QoS) Flow Identifier (QFI) information, steers packets to the correct output port, counts packets for charging and policy control, performs deep packet inspection for security and anomaly detection, and manages buffering and queuing for traffic differentiation and ensuring end-to-end delays.

Communication between UP and CP elements is achieved through point-to-point interfaces, each serving specific purposes, such as carrying user plane traffic (N3, N9, N6), managing mobility and session establishment (N1, N2), and managing UPFs (N4).

To access services provided by a Mobile Network Operator (MNO), the UE connects over the air interface to the gNB, and initiates Non-Access Stratum (NAS) signaling processing at the AMF and PDU session establishment. NFs in the SBA communicate with each other over the SBI using the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and secure connections via Transport Layer Security (TLS), or through reference points using specific transport and application layer protocols.

B. Non-3GPP Access Networks

To support the connectivity of UE via a non-3GPP access network, 5G systems specify three types of access: trusted, wireline, and untrusted [6]. Trusted access, standardized in 3GPP Rel-16, implies a high trust level where the operator has control over the non-3GPP network, such as a Trusted WLAN Access Network (TWAN). This type of access involves components like the Trusted Non-3GPP Access Point (TNAP) and the Trusted Non-3GPP Gateway Function (TNGF), enabling seamless UE connection to the 5GCN. Wireline access, also introduced in Rel-16, includes types like Wireline 5G Broadband Access Network (W-5GBAN) and Wireline 5G Cable Access Network (W-5GCAN), which connect via the Wireline Access Gateway Function (W-AGF). This access method supports legacy devices and Fixed Wireless Access (FWA), providing flexibility in connecting residential gateways to the 5GCN. In contrast, untrusted access, where the Mobile Network Operator (MNO) does not trust the security of the non-3GPP network, requires secure transport methods like the N3IWF. N3IWF acts as a gateway between the UE and the 5GCN, and is essential for integrating non-3GPP access technologies, such as Wi-Fi and fixed-line networks, into the 5GCN. It connects to the AMF via the N2 interface CP communication and to the UPF via the N3 interface for UP data traffic. After the UE undergoes authentication and authorization, it can access the 5GCN through the untrusted non-3GPP network, performing NAS signaling via the N1 interface. Data packets between the UE and the DN are transferred securely using an IPSec tunnel between the UE and N3IWF. Additionally, GTP-U establishes a tunnel between N3IWF and UPF for user data.

Accessing 5GCN from untrusted networks involves network access discovery and selection, registration, authentication, authorization, and PDU session establishment. To register to the 5GCN, the UE first needs to select and connect to a Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) using the WLAN protocol. Once the UE is configured with a local IP address from the selected WLAN, the UE selects the N3IWF and initiates the IPSec Security Association (SA) establishment procedure over the NWu interface using the IKEv2 protocol. After the IKEv2 SA establishment, the N3IWF starts the Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP-5G) procedure with the UE which initiates the registration and authentication procedure using the Non-Access Stratum (NAS) protocol with the AMF over N1 interface. The NAS messages are transported using the EAP-5G/IKEv2 between the N3IWF and UE over NWu interface and using the NGAP/SCTP protocol between the N3IWF and AMF over the N2 interface. Successful authentication involves AMF, AUSF, and UDM, resulting in a shared security key for NAS and N3IWF [7].

Finally, the PDU session establishment allows both UE and the network to initiate sessions for new connections or handovers. The UE-requested PDU session process

Figure 2: a) multi-technology access modelled as an open network of queues, b) Two-dimensional Markov Chain illustrating the Access network selection process for fast- and slow-moving mobile devices. The grey array illustrates the network states where 3GPP resources can be used by both

involves sending a request to the AMF via IPsec SA, which selects the SMF to create the PDU session context, authorize it, and establish IPsec child SAs for QoS profiles. Once the session is accepted, the N3IWF facilitates the secure data communication between the UE and the data network, encapsulating PDU sessions inside GRE tunnels [6][7].

III. RADIO ACCESS NETWORK SELECTION

We consider a multi-technology radio access network comprising 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies as shown in Figure 2a). For this network, end-to-end slices should be established interconnecting UEs with the DNs. In case where UEs are attached to the 3GPP access network, the corresponding slices will be established over the path 2-4-5 formed by interconnecting the gNB, UPF and DN nodes.

However, in case where UEs select a non-3GPP network, the relevant slices will be established over WiFi-N3IWF-UPF-DN (1-3-4-5) path. This network can be modeled as a mixed network of queues where new arriving UEs can be served either through the gNBs or the WiFi APs. In case of mobility handovers can be managed either maintaining the same access technology (i.e., handover from 3GPP to 3GPP) or forwarding connections to a different access network (i.e., handover from 3GPP to Non-3GPP and reverse).

In order to ensure seamless service provisioning, redundant physical resources should be reserved. The amount of redundant resources increases with the speed of end-user mobility, the size of the wireless cells (mobile users associated with small cells will exhibit very frequent handovers) and the traffic model adopted. Based on their technical characteristics, the wireless access technologies adopted in this work, can address end-user mobility with different levels of effectiveness, e.g. WiFi with smaller coverage can support users with relatively low mobility whereas gNBs with broader coverage can support higher mobility levels as less frequent handovers are required.

To maximize the benefits provided by the available technologies, users with low mobility and arrival rate λ_s can exclusively use the non-3GPP access. In addition to this, slow moving UEs can also use the 3GPP network which is shared with fast moving users that arrive in the system with rate λ_f . Fast users can access only 3GPP network resources. The overall network selection scheme is illustrated in the simple two-dimensional Markov Chain (MC) shown in Figure 2b). The state space of the MC model is defined as $\mathcal{S} = \{(i, j) | i \leq J, j \leq J\}$, where i, j correspond to the number of Non-3GPP and 3GPP users, respectively, and (i, j) is a feasible state in \mathcal{S} . In this scheme, we observe that if the total number of slow and fast mobile moving UEs in the network is less than a threshold (i.e., $i + j < C_{th}$), then access to 3GPP resources is granted to both type of users. However, above this threshold, access to 3GPP resources is permitted only to fast moving users. The main rationale behind this approach is that by reserving resources in the 3GPP access for fast mobile UEs, handover frequencies are reduced. It is clear that by reducing this threshold more resources in the 3GPP access can be allocated to serve fast moving UEs reducing the probability their QoS requirements not to be met and dropped. However, this comes at the cost of increased blocking for slow moving users. To address this problem, an optimal point that minimizes the weighted sum of normalized blocking and dropping ratio for slow and fast moving UEs, respectively, can be identified.

In the following subsection, a description of the testbed used to benchmark the proposed framework is proposed.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

In this section we provide an overview of the implementation that was carried out in this work. The main idea was to design and deploy a 5G platform that offers

Figure 3: Network Traffic for a UE that switches access network: a) from non-3gpp to 3gpp, b) UPF total, c) from 3gpp to non-3gpp, d) UPF total

multi-access UE connectivity in an environment where the 5G components are implemented as VNFs that run over a cloud infrastructure. At the same time, by extensively profiling each of the functionalities of the 5G system, we can determine critical parameters such as the downtime between switching access technologies, as well as measure the performance and consumption in terms of network, compute and memory. These parameters can then be mapped to the AN selection model in order to provide realistic values to its variables.

The lab testbed that was used for the implementation of this work, consists of the following:

- *A Private Cloud Platform:* The cloud platform provides the underlying environment on top of which the 5G VNFs are deployed. It based on openstack and all it functionalities run as microservices on LXD containers that are hosted the bare metal servers (Linux OS).
- *A Monitoring/Visualization Platform:* The monitoring platform extracts resource consumption metrics from all physical and virtual components and stores them in a Prometheus database. From there, the data can either retrieved or visualized (Grafana).

A. Deployment Overview

The network topology is illustrated in Figure 1 where five instances are used to host the VNFs and their interfaces. The deployment leverages the CP/UP split paradigm which enables flexibility and isolation of the NFs, while at the same time makes it possible to place the UPF node closer to the users in order to handle delay-constrained scenarios. Moreover, the network setup is in accordance with the SBA. All external interfaces are implemented in dedicated network subnets, enhancing security as well as ease of monitoring.

More specifically, the deployment includes:

Figure 4: CPU utilization for the physical machine hosting the UPF under various combinations of incoming 3GPP and Non-3GPP users

Figure 5: Optimal capacity threshold for different arrival rates

- *A 5GC CP VNF.* For the 5G CN, we used free5gc [15] which is an open-source for the core network, written in go. Most of the CP NFs use internal SBIs except from the SMF which uses the N4 subnet for the Packet Forwarding Control Protocol (PFCP), and the AMF which uses the N2 subnet for the Next Generation Application Protocol (NGAP).
- *A UPF VNF.* As mentioned above, the UPF node is deployed in a separate instance following the CUPS architecture. Three interfaces are attached to the node, a N3 interface for the GTP-U, a N4 for the PFCP and a N6 interface to provide connectivity with the Data Network.
- *A N3IWF VNF.* The N3IWF acts as gateway with the untrusted access network. For this reason, it is also implemented in a dedicated instance. It connects with the AMF via the N2 interface and with the UPF with N3. Additionally, it connected with an IPsec tunnel to the NWu node which is realized by the xfrm module.
- *A NWu interface.* The NWu is deployed in a separate machine. Typically, this machine is

interconnected with the Access Point (e.g. Wifi), where the traffic is bound with the IPsec tunnel in order to reach the 5G CN.

- *Emulated RAN and UE.* The UE and RAN part are based on UERANSIM [16]. The node is connected with the N1, N2 and N3 subnets.

B. Evaluation

After successful deployment of all instances we generate some network traffic from the UEs connected to each access network. The resulting graphs are shown in Figure 3 where network traffic is captured at different parts of the network. In Figure 3 a) and c) the purple color represents the traffic generated from the RAN-connected UE and the orange color indicates the non-3GPP UE. Figure 3 b) and d) depicts the network traffic captures at the UPF node (red color). In Figure 3 a) the UE is first connected to the 3GPP AN and after a while it connects to the 5G-RAN. The process is repeated in reverse in Figure 3 c). It is worth mentioning that the time needed to switch from RAN to non-3GPP AN is higher due to the security mechanisms implemented for the untrusted networks (GRE, IPsec, IKE etc.). Moreover, some minor differences observed between the traffic in the UE and the UPF are attributed in the existence of background traffic.

C. Optimal threshold identification for the radio access network selection process.

To identify the optimal threshold for the radio network access selection process described in the previous section we initially benchmark our network in order to evaluate for different arrival rates the corresponding service rates of the system. Based on the system's current configuration, the main bottleneck is associated with the VM hosting the UPF nodes used to serve both 3GPP and Non-3GPP connections. An example of the CPU utilization for the VM hosting the UPF for different combinations of incoming connections is shown in Figure 4. UEs connected to the system request the establishment of a service slice with 50Mbps throughput. When only 3GPP connections are established, the utilization of the CPU reaches 33% for 4 UEs. In case where the same number of UEs are connected through the Non-3GPP access, the CPU utilization increases to 44%. The latter is explained by the existence of multiple traffic flows and the increased complexity of the implementation compared to standard single-RAN deployments. A mixture of 3GPP and Non-3GPP traffic introduces further overhead to the system leading to a CPU utilization exceeding 56% for the same number of UEs (2 UEs connected through 3GPP and 2 through non-3GPP).

Once the service rates for the corresponding system have been determined, in the next step the optimal radio access selection threshold is determined. Figure 5 illustrates the normalized dropping and blocking rates for the fast and slow moving UEs, respectively. Numerical results have been extracted for a system that can host up to 10 UEs. As the capacity threshold increases, the gNB resources that can be exclusively used by the fast moving UEs are reduced leading to an increase of the number

connections whose QoS requirements are not met and, consequently, are dropped. However, this policy benefits the slow moving UEs leading to a reduction of their corresponding blocking ratio. Finally, we observe that an increase of the arrival rate of the of the fast moving UEs results to a decrease of the capacity threshold used by the proposed mechanism.

V. CONCLUSION

The integration of 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies in a multi-technology radio access network is crucial for addressing the diverse demands of modern communication. Utilizing the N3IWF enables seamless connectivity and secure access to the 5G Core. This paper explores such a network, focusing on minimizing handover interruptions through experimental data derived from an open-source 5G platform deployed in our private lab. Our findings, based on real user mobility statistics and lab profiling measurements, highlight resource consumption across both non-3GPP and 5G networks. By applying queuing theory, we derive valuable insights into E2E performance and optimize handover processes to enhance user experience.

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REFERENCES

- [1] "3GPP TS 23.502 version 15.3.0 Release 15, '5G;Procedures for the 5G System', " [Online].
- [2] 5G; NR; NR and NG-RAN Overall description; Stage-2, ETSI TS 138 300 V16.4.0 (2021c). [Online]
- [3] "Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV); Terminology for Main Concepts in NFV, ETSI GS NFV 003 V1.2.1 (2014). [Online]."
- [4] "Rommer, S., Hedman, P., Olsson, M., Frid, L., Sultana, S., Mulligan, C., 5G Core Networks: Powering Digitalization, ISBN: 9780081030097, Elsevier Science, 2019."
- [5] F. T. Kuhn, F. Schnicke and P. O. Antonino, "Service-Based Architectures in Production Systems: Challenges, Solutions & Experiences," in ITU Kaleidoscope: Industry-Driven Digital Transformation (ITU K), Ha Noi, Vietnam, 2020.
- [6] M. T. Lemes, A. M. Alberti, C. B. Both, A. C. De Oliveira Júnior and K. V. Cardoso, "A Tutorial on Trusted and Untrusted Non-3GPP Accesses in 5G Systems—First Steps Toward a Unified Communications Infrastructure," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 116662-116685, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3219829.
- [7] "Interworking of Untrusted Non-3GPP Networks and the 5G-Core Network." Wipro. Accessed July 15, 2024. <https://www.wipro.com/network-edge-providers/untrusted-non-3gpp-access-network-interworking-with-5g-core/>.
- [8] Matan Broner, Sangwoo Lee, Liuyi Jin, and Radu Stoleru. 2023. Poster: Towards Multi-Radio Access in 5G Networks. In Proceedings of the 21st Annual International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications and Services (MobiSys '23). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 575–576. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3581791.3597373>
- [9] M. Müller *et al.*, "LiFi with 5G for the Smart Factory," *2022 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, Austin, TX, USA, 2022, pp. 2310-2315, doi: 10.1109/WCNC51071.2022.9771969.
- [10] M. Luglio, M. Quadri, C. Roseti, D. Verde and F. Zampognaro, "Performance evaluation of untrusted non-3GPP Access to a 5G Core Network via satellite," *2022 International Symposium on*

Networks, Computers and Communications (ISNCC), Shenzhen, China, 2022, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ISNCC55209.2022.9851800.

- [11] V. Agarwal, C. Sharma, R. Shetty, A. Jangam and R. Asati, "A Journey Towards a Converged 5G Architecture & Beyond," *2021 IEEE 4th 5G World Forum (5GWF)*, Montreal, QC, Canada, 2021, pp. 18-23, doi: 10.1109/5GWF52925.2021.00011.
- [12] S. Chandrashekar, A. Maeder, C. Sartori, T. Höhne, B. Vejlgard and D. Chandramouli, "5G multi-RAT multi-connectivity architecture," *2016 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC)*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 2016, pp. 180-186, doi: 10.1109/ICCW.2016.7503785.
- [13] T. Metin, M. Emmelmann, M. Corici, V. Jungnickel, C. Kottke and M. Müller, "Integration of Optical Wireless Communication with 5G Systems," *2020 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, Taipei, Taiwan, 2020, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/GCWkshps50303.2020.9367502.
- [14] Marin, A., Meo, M., Sereno, M., & Marsan, M. A. (2024). Queuing Network Models of Multiservice RANs. *ACM Transactions on Modeling and Performance Evaluation of Computing Systems*, 9(2), 1-26.
- [15] Free5gc, [online]. Available: <https://free5gc.org/>
- [16] UERANSIM, [online]. Available: <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>
- [17] H. Koumaras, et.al., "5G-Enabled UAVs with Command and Control Software Component at the Edge for Supporting Energy Efficient Opportunistic Networks." *Energies* **2021**, 14, 1480.
- [18] H. Koumaras *et al.*, "A network programmability framework for vertical applications in the beyond 5G era," *2022 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, Grenoble, France, 2022, pp. 375-380